

SA 51P1-7

SA 51P2-19

SA51-p1-80

SA 51-111

SA 51-144

SA 51-146

SA 51-160

SA 51-166

SA 51-182

SA 51p1-222

SA 51p1-258

SA 51P1-274

SA 51P1-277

SA 51P1-287

SA 51P2-40

SA 51p2-46

SA 51P2-48

SA 51P2-52

SA 51P2-56

SA 51p2-58

SA 51p2-93

SA 51p2-102

SA 51p2-106

SA 51P2-110
Mislabelled..
Should be
SA811p2-110

SA 51P2-133

SA 51p2-141

SA 51p2-204

SA 51p2-230

SA 51P2-246

SA 51P2-286

SA 22-s1-2

SA 22-34

SA22 s1-18

SA 22-s1-53

SA22 s1-40

SA 22-47

SA22 s1-44

SA 22-57

SA 22s1-51

SA 22-s1-59

SA 22-42

SA 22-184

SA22-47

SA22-57

SA22-S1-59

SA22-60

SA 22-113

SA 22-165

SA 22-176

SA 22-196

SA 22-212

SA811p1-6

SA811p1-7

811p1-9

811-p1 -10

sa811p1-27

SA811p1-31

SA811p1-33

811p1-38

SA811p1-46

Sa811p1-52

SA811p1-54

SA811p1-59

SA811p1-61

SA811p1-73

SA811p1-74

SA811p1-78

SA811p1-82

SA811p1-85

SA811p1-86

SA811p1-93

SA811p1-95

SA811p1-97

SA811p1-107

SA811p1-113

SA811p1-120

SA811p1-133

SA811p1-139

SA811p1-149

SA811p1-152

SA811p1-163

SA811p1-164

SA811p1-166

SA811p1-168

SA811p1-174

SA811p1-198

SA811p1-204

SA811p1-210

SA811p1-236

SA811p1-239

SA811p1-265

SA811p1-277

SA811p1-286

SA811p1-292

SA811p1-293

SA811p1-296

SA811p1-297

SA811p1-298

SA811p1-299

SA811p1-300

SA811p1-304

SA811p1-315

SA811p2-5

SA811p2-13

SA811p2-18

SA 811p2-21

SA811p2-30 and 31

SA811p2-42

SA811p2-44

SASA811P1-46

SA811P2-57

SA811P2-61

SA811p2-71

SA811p2-89

GB16-1 -
SA811p2-99grain1

SA811P2-99grain2

SA811P2-128

SA811p2-131

GB16-1
SA811p2-137

GB-17-6
SA811P2-137

SA811p2-143

SA811P2-156

SA811p2-158

SA811p2 -163, 187, and 193

SA811p2-167

SA811p2-186

SA811p2-192

SA811p2-193

SA811p2-204

SA811P2-215

SA811
p2-
197

SA811p2-206

NAD-106L

106-1L-76

106-1L-226

106-1L-205

106-1L-147

106-1L-144

106-1L-143

106-1L-207

106-1L-96

NAD-106-2L-120

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 173 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.88 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-2L-118

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 302 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.08 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-2L-103

NAD-106-2L-82

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 305 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.07 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-2-11

NAD-106-2L-121

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 302 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.08 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-2-133

NAD-106-2L-127

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 113 µm	Det: CL	20 µm
SEM MAG: 2.88 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20	USGS

NAD-106-2L-130

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 279 µm	Det: CL	50 µm
SEM MAG: 1.17 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20	USGS

NAD-106-2L-134

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 172 µm	Det: CL	50 µm
SEM MAG: 1.89 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20	USGS

NAD-106-2L-142

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 182 µm	Det: CL	50 µm
SEM MAG: 1.78 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20	USGS

NAD-106-3L-6

NAD-106-3L-21

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.72 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN	SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 94.7 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS	View field: 110 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 3.43 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20			SEM MAG: 2.94 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		

NAD-106-3L-25

NAD-106-3L-29

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN	SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 119 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS	View field: 122 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 2.74 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20			SEM MAG: 2.66 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		

NAD-106-3L-31

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.81 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 140 μm	Det: CL	20 μm	
SEM MAG: 2.33 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-32

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.81 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 113 μm	Det: CL	20 μm	
SEM MAG: 2.89 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-33

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 148 μm	Det: CL	20 μm	
SEM MAG: 2.20 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-43

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 211 μm	Det: CL	50 μm	
SEM MAG: 1.54 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-8

NAD-106-3L-46

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 82.5 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 3.94 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-48

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 104 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 3.14 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-50

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 104 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 3.13 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-51

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 90.1 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 3.61 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-157

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 155 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 2.09 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-189

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 302 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.08 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-180

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 209 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.55 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-200

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 225 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.45 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-201

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 97.7 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 3.33 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-218

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 140 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 2.33 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-228

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 90.0 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 3.61 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-232

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 108 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 3.00 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-236

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 140 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 2.32 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-237

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 168 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.93 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-246

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 140 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 2.32 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-250

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 197 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.65 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-259

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 110 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 2.97 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-262

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 156 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 2.09 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-287

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 206 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.57 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-298

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 91.7 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 3.55 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-3L-302

NAD-106L-3-308

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 151 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 2.16 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.74 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 91.1 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 3.57 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		

NAD-106-4L-3

NAD-106-4L-6

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN	SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 168 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	View field: 123 µm	Det: CL	20 µm
SEM MAG: 1.93 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20	USGS	SEM MAG: 2.65 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20	USGS

NAD-106-4L-9

NAD-106-4L-12

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN	SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 131 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	View field: 204 µm	Det: CL	50 µm
SEM MAG: 2.48 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20	USGS	SEM MAG: 1.60 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20	USGS

NAD-106-4L-27

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 164 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.98 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-4L-30

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 169 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.93 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-4L-32

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 246 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.32 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-4L-37

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 150 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 2.17 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		USGS

NAD-106-4L-47

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 14.94 mm
View field: 121 μ m Det: CL 20 μ m
SEM MAG: 2.68 kx Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20

VEGA3 TESCAN
USGS

NAD-106-4L-51

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 14.94 mm
View field: 138 μ m Det: CL 20 μ m
SEM MAG: 2.35 kx Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20

VEGA3 TESCAN
USGS

NAD-106-4L-53

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 14.94 mm
View field: 150 μ m Det: CL 20 μ m
SEM MAG: 2.17 kx Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20

VEGA3 TESCAN
USGS

NAD-106-4L-52

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 14.94 mm
View field: 123 μ m Det: CL 20 μ m
SEM MAG: 2.64 kx Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20

VEGA3 TESCAN
USGS

NAD-106-4L-57

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 118 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 2.75 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		

NAD-106-4L-56

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 125 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 2.59 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		

NAD-106-4L-74

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 108 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 3.00 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		

NAD-106-4L-70

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 116 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 2.79 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		

NAD-106-4L-79

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 99.5 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 3.27 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		

NAD-106-4L-76

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 122 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 2.66 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		

NAD-106-4L-93

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 254 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 1.28 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		

NAD-106-4L-91

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 130 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 2.51 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		

NAD-106-4L-103

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.94 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 94.0 μm	Det: CL	20 μm	USGS
SEM MAG: 3.46 kx	Date(m/d/y): 03/09/20		

NAD-180#2-2-1-8

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 14.32 mm VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 399 µm Det: CL 100 µm
SEM MAG: 1.63 kx USGSUser USGS

NAD-180#2-2-1-46

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 14.32 mm VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 245 µm Det: CL 50 µm
SEM MAG: 2.65 kx USGSUser USGS

NAD-180#2-2-2-206

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 14.32 mm VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 371 µm Det: CL 100 µm
SEM MAG: 1.75 kx USGSUser USGS

NAD-180#2-2-2-196

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 14.32 mm VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 320 µm Det: CL 100 µm
SEM MAG: 2.03 kx USGSUser USGS

NAD-180#2-2-2-244

NAD-180#2-2-3-222

SEM HV: 12.0 kV	WD: 13.54 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 200 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.63 kx	Date(m/d/y): 10/04/18		USGS

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.32 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 367 µm	Det: CL	100 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.77 kx	USGSUser		USGS

NAD-180#2-2-2-267

NAD-180#2-2-2-271

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.32 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 473 µm	Det: CL	100 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.37 kx	USGSUser		USGS

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.32 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 318 µm	Det: CL	100 µm	
SEM MAG: 2.04 kx	USGSUser		USGS

NAD-180#2-2-2-291

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.32 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 405 μm	Det: CL	100 μm	
SEM MAG: 1.61 kx	USGSUser		USGS

NAD-180#2-2-2-309

NAD-180#2-2-2-134

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.32 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 399 μm	Det: CL	100 μm	
SEM MAG: 1.63 kx	USGSUser		USGS

NAD-180#2-1-188

SEM HV: 12.0 kV	WD: 13.27 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 114 μm	Det: CL	20 μm	
SEM MAG: 2.86 kx	Date(m/d/y): 10/04/18		USGS

NAD-180#2-2-2-188

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.32 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 473 μm	Det: CL	100 μm	
SEM MAG: 1.37 kx	USGSUser		USGS

NAD-180#2-2-1-56

SEM HV: 12.0 kV	WD: 13.45 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 200 µm	Det: CL	50 µm
SEM MAG: 1.63 kx	Date(m/d/y): 10/04/18	USGS

NAD-180#2-2-2-5

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.32 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 371 µm	Det: CL	100 µm
SEM MAG: 1.75 kx	USGSUser	USGS

NAD-180#2-2-2-7

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.32 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 367 µm	Det: CL	100 µm
SEM MAG: 1.77 kx	USGSUser	USGS

NAD-180#2-2-1-25

NAD-180#2-2-1-5

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.32 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 371 µm	Det: CL	100 µm
SEM MAG: 1.75 kx	USGSUser	USGS

NAD-106-0-
1-211

NAD-106-0-
1-136

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 12.95 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN	SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 12.95 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 304 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	USGS	View field: 513 µm	Det: CL	100 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 2.14 kx	USGSUser			SEM MAG: 1.27 kx	USGSUser		

NAD-106-0-
1-52

NAD-106-0-
1-66

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 12.95 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN	SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 12.95 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 160 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	USGS	View field: 112 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 4.06 kx	USGSUser			SEM MAG: 5.80 kx	USGSUser		

NAD-106-0-2-10

NAD-106-0-2-45

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 12.95 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN	SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 12.95 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 398 μm	Det: CL	100 μm	View field: 381 μm	Det: CL	100 μm
SEM MAG: 1.64 kx	USGSUser	USGS	SEM MAG: 1.71 kx	USGSUser	USGS

NAD-106-0-2-73

NAD-106-0-2-152

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 12.95 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN	SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 12.95 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 403 μm	Det: CL	100 μm	View field: 85.8 μm	Det: CL	20 μm
SEM MAG: 1.61 kx	USGSUser	USGS	SEM MAG: 7.58 kx	USGSUser	USGS

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 12.95 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 394 μ m	Det: CL	100 μ m
SEM MAG: 1.65 kx	USGSUser	USGS

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.49 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 100 μ m	Det: CL	20 μ m
SEM MAG: 3.25 kx	Date(m/d/y): 10/04/18	USGS

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 12.95 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 245 μ m	Det: CL	50 μ m
SEM MAG: 2.65 kx	USGSUser	USGS

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.49 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 100 μ m	Det: CL	20 μ m
SEM MAG: 3.25 kx	Date(m/d/y): 10/04/18	USGS

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 12.95 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 259 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 2.51 kx	USGSUser		

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.49 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 100 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 3.25 kx	Date(m/d/y): 10/04/18		

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 12.95 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 285 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 2.28 kx	USGSUser		

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 12.95 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 286 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 2.28 kx	USGSUser		

NAD-106-0-4-136

NAD-106-0-4-297

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 12.95 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN	SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.41 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 255 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	USGS	View field: 200 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 2.55 kx	USGSUser			SEM MAG: 1.63 kx	Date(m/d/y): 10/04/18		

NAD-106-0-5-18

NAD-106-0-5-62

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.45 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN	SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 12.95 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 150 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS	View field: 154 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 2.16 kx	Date(m/d/y): 10/04/18			SEM MAG: 4.23 kx	USGSUser		

NAD-106-0-
5-29

15kV

X370

50µm

42

38

AUX

NAD-106-0-
5-45

15kV

X250

100µm

42

38

AUX

NAD-106-100 Spot 1-50

NAD-106-100-1-254

NAD-106-100-1-264

NAD-106-100-1-268

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 13.03 mm VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 336 µm Det: CL 100 µm
SEM MAG: 1.94 kx USGSUser USGS

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 13.03 mm VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 458 µm Det: CL 100 µm
SEM MAG: 1.42 kx USGSUser USGS

NAD-106-100 -1-91

NAD-106-100-1-142

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 14.32 mm VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 420 µm Det: CL 100 µm
SEM MAG: 1.55 kx USGSUser USGS

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 14.32 mm VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 364 µm Det: CL 100 µm
SEM MAG: 1.79 kx USGSUser USGS

NAD-106-100-2-118

NAD-106-100-2-287

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.32 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN	SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.32 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 364 µm	Det: CL	100 µm	View field: 380 µm	Det: CL	100 µm
SEM MAG: 1.79 kx	USGSUser	USGS	SEM MAG: 1.71 kx	USGSUser	USGS

NAD-106-100-2-188

NAD-106-100-2-242

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.32 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN	SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 13.03 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 483 µm	Det: CL	100 µm	View field: 237 µm	Det: CL	50 µm
SEM MAG: 1.35 kx	USGSUser	USGS	SEM MAG: 2.74 kx	USGSUser	USGS

NAD-106-200-1-50

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 14.51 mm VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 298 µm Det: CL 50 µm
SEM MAG: 2.18 kx USGSUser USGS

NAD-106-200-1-72

SEM HV: 12.0 kV WD: 15.33 mm VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 150 µm Det: CL 20 µm
SEM MAG: 2.16 kx Date(m/d/y): 10/09/18 USGS

NAD-106-200-3-131

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 14.51 mm VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 306 µm Det: CL 50 µm
SEM MAG: 2.13 kx USGSUser USGS

NAD-106-200-1-108

NAD-106-200-1-168

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 14.51 mm VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 408 µm Det: CL 100 µm
SEM MAG: 1.59 kx USGSUser USGS

NAD-106-200-1-70

15kV

X400 100µm

42 39 AUX

NAD-106-200-1-14

NAD-106-200-1-89

15kV

X230 100µm

42 39 AUX

NAD-106-
200-1-211

NAD-106-
200-2-73

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.51 mm		VEGA3 TESCAI
View field: 296 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 2.20 kx	USGSUser		

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.51 mm		VEGA3 TESCAI
View field: 223 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 2.92 kx	USGSUser		

NAD-106-
200-2-185

NAD-106-
200-2-185

NAD-106-
200-2-211

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.51 mm		VEGA3 TESCAI
View field: 136 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 4.79 kx	USGSUser		

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.51 mm		VEGA3 TESCAI
View field: 539 µm	Det: CL	100 µm	USGS
SEM MAG: 1.21 kx	USGSUser		

NAD-106-200-2-45

15kV

X300

50µm

42 39 AUX

NAD-106-200-2-54

15kV

X190

100µm

42 39 AUX

NAD-106-500-1-36

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.51 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 383 µm	Det: CL	100 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.70 kx	USGSUser		USGS

NAD-106-500-1-92

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.51 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 125 µm	Det: CL	20 µm	
SEM MAG: 5.21 kx	USGSUser		USGS

NAD-106-500-1-163

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.51 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 192 µm	Det: CL	50 µm	
SEM MAG: 3.39 kx	USGSUser		USGS

NAD-106-500-1-210

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.51 mm		VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 383 µm	Det: CL	100 µm	
SEM MAG: 1.70 kx	USGSUser		USGS

NAD-106-
500-1-158

15kV

X270

50µm

42 39 AUX

NAD-106-500-1-179

15kV

X400

50µm 0000

NAD106-1-299

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.51 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 88.5 μ m	Det: CL	20 μ m
SEM MAG: 7.35 kx	USGSUser	USGS

NAD-106-500-1-302

SEM HV: 10.0 kV	WD: 14.51 mm	VEGA3 TESCAN
View field: 107 μ m	Det: CL	20 μ m
SEM MAG: 6.10 kx	USGSUser	USGS

NAD-106-500-2-46

15kV

X250 100µm

42 39 AUX

NAD-106-500-2-93

15kV

X250 100µm

42 39 AUX

